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Approximate analytical solution for solidification of PCM in cylindrical geometry with temperature-dependent thermal conductivity-perturbation method

Milad Tajik Jamal-Abad*, Cristóbal Cortés, Javier Pallarés Ranz and Antonia Gil

University of Zaragoza- IUI mixto CIRCE, Campus Río Ebro. Building B. María de Luna s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

Email: mtajikjamalabad@unizar.es

Abstract. The Solidification process of Phase change materials inside cylindrical enclosures is analyzed and analytical solutions are derived to determine the positions of the interfaces at different time intervals. In this current investigation, we address the scenario involving temperature-dependent thermal conductivity. For the first time, we employ perturbation techniques to analytically derive the dimensional temperature for both phases. Our study specifically incorporates a linear model to account for the variation in thermal conductivity with temperature. The results show that the duration of complete solidification relies on the Stefan number. As these parameter is augmented, the total solidification time of the cylinder diminishes and escalates, respectively. Furthermore, it has been observed that an augmentation in the thermal conductivity of the phase change material (PCM) leads to a swifter solidification process.

1. Introduction

Because of the non-linear nature of the solid-liquid interface and constraints like geometry, temperature fluctuations, and movements in the liquid phase, the majority of research employs numerical or finite difference methods. Solutions to these solid-liquid phase change processes are commonly known as Stefan problems [1,2]. Many approximate analytical solutions exist, employing diverse mathematical techniques like the variational approach, Megerlin method, perturbation, heat balance integral method, and quasi-steady approximation for phase change problems, without taking into account heat generation. Perturbation series analysis for heat transfer applications have proven to be an effective and versatile tool in developing accurate solutions for wide variety of problems [3,4]. Kumar et al. [5] delved into the Stefan problem with phase change, incorporating time and temperature-dependent thermal conductivity. Their investigation utilized similarity transformation and the tau method, leveraging the shifted Chebyshev operational matrix of differentiation. Ceretani et al. [6] addressed a phase change issue with thermal conductivity dependent on temperature. They introduced a Robin condition at the stationary face. Kumar et al. [7] examined the Stefan problem, considering both thermal conductivity and heat capacity as functions of temperature. They provided exact solutions for specific cases using the similarity variables method. Calvo-Schwarzwalder [8] investigated a mathematical model for a one-dimensional solidification process with thermal conductivity dependent on size. They incorporated a Newton cooling condition at the fixed boundary. The study proposed and compared numerical and asymptotic solution methods, which demonstrated good agreement within the range of considered

parameters. In Font's study [9], an analysis of a one-phase Stefan problem was conducted, taking into account thermal conductivity dependent on size. The study also delved into the discussion of approximate solutions to this problem through perturbation and numerical methods.

2. Mathematical modelling

Initially, the cylinder's temperature is T_i , which is higher than the fusion temperature T_f , while the surface temperature of the cylinder is maintained at T_o , which is lower than T_f . This problem will be resolved in the presence of heat generation and the energy is generated throughout the cylinder at a constant volumetric rate \dot{q} . Due to symmetry, the center line at $r^* = 0$ is insulated, and hence half of the cylinder is considered for analysis as shown in figure 1. The process of solidification commences at the surface of the cylinder, where a dynamic solidification front emerges instantaneously and advances through the liquid phase. To simplify the problem, the changes of volume on solidification are neglected and the properties are same in both solid and liquid phases.

Based on these assumptions, the governing heat equations for solidification are

$$\frac{\partial T_S}{\partial t^*} = \frac{\dot{q}}{\rho c} + \alpha \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(r^* k \frac{\partial T_S}{\partial r^*} \right) \quad \sigma \leq r^* \leq R \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_L}{\partial t^*} = \frac{\dot{q}}{\rho c} + \alpha \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(r^* k \frac{\partial T_L}{\partial r^*} \right) \quad 0 \leq r^* \leq \sigma \quad (2)$$

Where α is thermal diffusivity, ρ is density, c is specific heat, and the subscripts S and L represents solid and liquid phase, respectively. The boundary conditions are,

$$T_S(r^* = R, t) = T_o, T_S(r^* = \sigma, t) = T_f, T_L(r^* = \sigma, t) = T_f, \frac{\partial T_L(r^* = 0, t)}{\partial r^*} = 0$$

The initial conditions are,

$$T_L(r^*, t = 0) = T_i, \sigma(t = 0) = R$$

The interface energy balance between the solid and liquid phase along the solidification front,

$$k \frac{\partial T_S(r^* = \sigma, t)}{\partial r^*} - k \frac{\partial T_L(r^* = \sigma, t)}{\partial r^*} = \rho H \frac{d\sigma}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Where k is thermal conductivity, H is latent heat of fusion, and σ is solidification front position.

Dimensionless variables are employed, and the governing equation, along with the boundary conditions, initial conditions, and interface energy balance equation, are transformed into dimensionless form. The quantities in this context are expressed in dimensionless terms.

$$r = \frac{r^*}{R}, \quad s = \frac{\sigma}{R}, \quad \theta_S = \frac{T_f - T_S}{T_f - T_o}, \quad \theta_L = \frac{T_f - T_L}{T_f - T_o}, \quad Fo = \varepsilon \frac{at}{R^2}, \quad \beta = \frac{R^2 \dot{q}}{k(T_f - T_o)} \quad (4)$$

here θ_S and θ_L are dimensionless solid and liquid temperature, respectively. The dependency of the conductivity to the temperature is modelled by:

$$k = k_r \left(1 + \varepsilon \frac{T_f - T_{S,L}}{T_f - T_o} \right) \quad (5)$$

k_r is the reference thermal conductivity, ε is the linear dependency multiplier ($\varepsilon < 1$).

By applying equation (4) the non-dimensional form equation (1) and equation (2) becomes

$$(1 + \varepsilon \theta_S) \frac{\partial^2 \theta_S}{\partial r^2} + \frac{(1 + \varepsilon \theta_S)}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_S}{\partial r} + \varepsilon \left(\frac{\partial \theta_S}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \beta = \varepsilon \frac{\partial \theta_S}{\partial Fo} \quad s \leq r \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon \theta_L) \frac{\partial^2 \theta_L}{\partial r^2} + \frac{(1 + \varepsilon \theta_L)}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_L}{\partial r} + \varepsilon \left(\frac{\partial \theta_L}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \beta = \varepsilon \frac{\partial \theta_L}{\partial Fo} \quad 0 \leq r^* \leq s \quad (7)$$

Similarly the non-dimensional boundary and initial conditions,

$$\theta_S(r = 1, Fo) = 1, \theta_S(r = s, Fo) = 0, \theta_L(r = s, Fo) = 0, \frac{\partial \theta_L(r = 0, Fo)}{\partial r} = 0, \theta_L(r, Fo = 0) = \theta_i, s(Fo = 0) = 1$$

Interface energy equation (3) transforms to,

$$Ste \left(\frac{\partial \theta_s(s, Fo)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial \theta_L(s, Fo)}{\partial r} \right) = \frac{-ds}{dFo} \quad (8)$$

where, Ste is the Stefan number defined as, $Ste = \frac{c(T_f - T_0)}{H}$.

3. Analysis and solution

One approach is to simplify the problem by assuming quasi-stationarity, allowing us to neglect the transient terms. The quasi-steady model holds validity for low values of the Stefan number ($Ste < 1$) [10]. The interface energy equation remains unaltered. Due to the negligible influence of transient terms, the steady-state temperature distribution is promptly achieved as the interface advances.

The energy equations described above are tackled analytically through the perturbation method. In this investigation, the Stefan number (Ste) is chosen to assume this role [11]. This dimensionless factor signifies the comparative significance of stored sensible heat in relation to stored latent heat. The temperature field is assumed to have the following form

$$\theta = \theta_0 + \varepsilon \theta_1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \quad (9)$$

For solid phase:

$$\mathcal{O}(0): \quad \frac{\partial^2 \theta_{s0}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_{s0}}{\partial r} + \beta = 0 \quad \theta_{s0}(1) = 1, \theta_{s0}(s) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon): \quad \frac{\partial^2 \theta_{s1}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_{s1}}{\partial r} + \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{s1}}{\partial r} \right)^2 = 0 \quad \theta_{s1}(1) = 0, \theta_{s1}(s) = 0 \quad (11)$$

For liquid phase:

$$\mathcal{O}(0): \quad \frac{\partial^2 \theta_{L0}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_{L0}}{\partial r} + \beta = 0 \quad \theta_{L0}(1) = 1, \theta_{L0}(s) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon): \quad \frac{\partial^2 \theta_{L1}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta_{L1}}{\partial r} + \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{L1}}{\partial r} \right)^2 = 0 \quad \theta_{L1}(1) = 0, \theta_{L1}(s) = 0 \quad (13)$$

The solution will be obtained for both phases separately:

$$\theta_s = \theta_{s0} + \varepsilon \theta_{s1} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_s = & \frac{1}{4} \beta r^2 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{(\beta s^2 + 4 - \beta) \ln(r)}{\ln(s)} + 1 - \frac{1}{4} B \\ & + \varepsilon \left(\frac{1}{64} \frac{1}{\ln(s)^2} ((32 \ln(s) + 3\beta^2 s^4 \ln(s) - 4\beta^2 s^4 - 16\beta s^2 + 8\beta^2 s^2 + 16\beta s^2 \ln(s)) \right. \\ & - 4 \ln(s) \beta^2 s^2 - 16\beta \ln(s) + \ln(s) \beta^2 + 16\beta - 4\beta^2) \ln(r) - \frac{1}{64} \beta^2 r^4 + \frac{1}{16} \frac{\beta^2 r^2 s^2}{\ln(s)} \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta r^2}{\ln(s)} - \frac{1}{16} \frac{\beta^2 r^2}{\ln(s)} - \frac{1}{32} \frac{\beta^2 s^4 \ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} - \frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta s^2 \ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} + \frac{1}{16} \frac{\beta^2 s^2 \ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta \ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} - \frac{1}{32} \frac{\beta^2 \ln(r)^2}{\ln(s)^2} + \frac{1}{64} \frac{\beta(\beta \ln(s) - 4\beta s^2 - 16 + 4\beta)}{\ln(s)} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\theta_L = \theta_{L0} + \varepsilon \theta_{L1} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$$

$$\theta_L = \frac{B}{4} (r^2 - s^2) + \frac{\varepsilon B^2}{64} (s^4 - r^4) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \quad (15)$$

Differentiating equation (14) and equation (15), and substituting into interface equation (8), with applying the initial conditions ($Fo = 0$) = 1), results in

$$\frac{-ds}{dFo} = \frac{-Ste(Bs^2 + 4 - B)}{s \ln(s)} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \quad (16)$$

$$Ste \int_0^{Fo} dFo = \frac{4}{B} \int_1^s \frac{s \ln(s) ds}{s^2 + (4/B - 1)} \quad (17)$$

It is worthwhile to mention that as assumption Stefan number and linear dependency multiplier have same order ($\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$), hence when they multiply together the order became $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$ and we can ignore them. From equation (17), it is clear that the above integral has to be evaluated in three cases ($\beta < 4, \beta = 4, \beta > 4$). S. Kalaiselvam et al [10] proposed a 3 different equations for these situations

Case 1: $\beta < 4$

$$Ste Fo = \frac{4}{\beta} \left[\frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_1 + si}{a_1}\right) + \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_1 - si}{a_1}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \ln(s) \ln\left(\frac{a_1 + si}{a_1}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \ln(s) \ln\left(\frac{a_1 - si}{a_1}\right) - \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_1 - i}{a_1}\right) - \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_1 + i}{a_1}\right) \right] \tag{18}$$

Where $a_1 = \sqrt{4/\beta - 1}$, $dilog(x)$ is a special mathematical function defined by the analytical continuation of the following integral [11]. $dilog(x) = -\int_0^x \frac{\log(1-t)}{t} dt$ for a real number $x < 1$. These functions are evaluated by using mfun function of MATLAB v7.0 (R14), with an accuracy of 10^{-16} .

Case 2: $\beta > 4$

$$Ste \int_0^{Fo} dFo = \frac{4}{B} \int_1^s \frac{s \ln(s) ds}{s^2 - (1 - 4/B)}$$

$$Ste Fo = \frac{4}{\beta} \left[\frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_2 + s}{a_2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_2 - s}{a_2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \ln(s) \ln\left(\frac{a_2 + s}{a_2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \ln(s) \ln\left(\frac{a_2 - s}{a_2}\right) - \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_2 - 1}{a_2}\right) - \frac{1}{2} dilog\left(\frac{a_2 + 1}{a_2}\right) \right] \tag{19}$$

Where $a_2 = \sqrt{1 - 4/\beta}$

Case 3: $\beta = 4$

$$Ste Fo = \frac{1}{2} (\ln(s))^2 \tag{20}$$

4. Results and discussion

Figure 2 illustrates the comparison between the perturbation analysis and the analytical method introduced by Barba and Spiga [12] for determining the transient interface locations within a cylindrical enclosure in the absence of any heat generation $\beta = 0$. What stands from the graph is that for basic situation ($\beta = 0$ and $\varepsilon = 0$) there is a precise alignment between the referenced solution and the demonstrated solution, confirming its validity

Figure 1. Sectional model of the cylindrical PCM

Figure 2. Comparison between analytical solutions with literature [19]

Under the assumption that $\varepsilon = 0$, the temperature distribution for both phases (equation (14) and equation (15)). reduces to $\theta = \theta_0$. These values were previously calculated for a constant thermal conductivity and reported in the prior literature [10]. The transient solid and liquid temperature profiles

for various values of β are shown in figure 3. When there is an increase in dimensionless heat generation, the solidification rate decreases (slower rate of solidification). Conversely, higher values of the Stefan number (Ste) are associated with faster rates of solidification. Moreover, the dimensionless temperature profile for both constant and variable conductivity assumptions ($\varepsilon = 0$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$ and $\varepsilon = 0.2$) is depicted in figure 3. Although the influence of variable conductivity on the liquid phase is minimal, this parameter has a more pronounced effect on the dimensionless temperature within the solid phase. The ratio of thermal conductivity between the solid and liquid phases directly reflects the speed at which the solidification process takes place. A higher ratio of thermal conductivity leads to a swifter movement of the interface, resulting in a more rapid temperature decrease, as illustrated in figure 3. Another fact can be seen is that, the impact of variable thermal conductivity on temperature profile increases by rising β , this is due to the fact that the increased heat generation leads to a more substantial heat source within the system.

Figure 3. Transient temperature profiles. a) $\beta = 1$, b) $\beta = 3$, c) $\beta = 5$

The influence of variable conductivity assumptions on the transient interface position for $\beta = 0$ is depicted in figure 4. It is evident that an increase in ε leads to an enhancement in the solidification rate. For instance, assuming a constant Stefan number, the Fourier number decreases by approximately 13% for complete solidification when comparing $\varepsilon = 0$ and $\varepsilon = 0.3$. Indeed, larger values of thermal conductivity facilitate more efficient heat transfer between the two phases and with the surrounding environment. Figure 5 shows that when heat generation values exceed 4.0 ($\beta > 4.0$), a stable state is achieved even without complete solidification. Conversely, when heat generation values are below 4.0 ($\beta < 4.0$), the material fully solidifies but a stable state is not reached. In the unique scenario where β equals 4.0, complete solidification coincides with the establishment of a stable state.

Figure 4. Impact of variable conductivity on transient interface position ($\beta = 0$)

Figure 5. Transient interface positions for various heat generation parameter

The figure 6 clearly illustrates that heat generation has the effect of slowing down the motion of the interface. This is because higher levels of heat generation demand more substantial heat extraction from the surface, which is necessary for the growth of the solidification layer. Another intriguing observation is that an accelerated solidification process occurs with an increase in the thermal conductivity of the phase change material (PCM). In the context of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) applications, it can be deduced that the TES storage can undergo solidification to an approximate extent of 80%, rather than achieving complete solidification. The impact of both thermal conductivity and heat generation on the degree of solidification is depicted in figure 7. Notably, increased heat generation exerts a negative influence on the rates of both charging and discharging, with these rates escalating as β values rise.

Conversely, the enhancement of thermal conductivity leads to a reduction in the rates of both charging and discharging

Figure 6. Impact of variable conductivity on transient interface position

Figure 7. Effect of thermal conductivity and heat generation on percentage solidification

5. Conclusion

The study delves into the solidification behaviors of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) confined within cylinders, considering a temperature-dependent thermal conductivity. Analytical models have been developed and compared with experimental data to assess front positions. In terms of predicting interface positions during solidification, the analytical model incorporating heat generation proves to be effective. The energy equation has been addressed using perturbation techniques. The rationale behind adopting a linear assessment of thermal conductivity has been elucidated, and parametric investigations reveal that solidification rates escalate proportionally with an increase in thermal conductivity. It has been found that the solidification process occurs rapidly with an increase in the thermal conductivity of the phase change material (PCM). For higher values of β , this phenomena is considerably more evident.

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